

A New Look into NASA's Pioneering Atomic Oxygen Treatment Removing Lipstick Defacement from Andy Warhol's "Bathtub"

Tomas Markevicius,⁽¹⁾ Ilaria Bonaduce,⁽²⁾ Anton Nikiforov,⁽³⁾ Nina Olsson,⁽⁴⁾ Agnieszka Suliga,⁽⁵⁾ Silvia Pizzimenti,⁽⁶⁾ Gianluca Pastorelli,⁽⁷⁾ Nan Yang⁽⁸⁾

(1,3) Ghent University (2,5) University of Pisa (4,6) ICOMOS Lithuania (5) European Space Agency ESA (7) National Gallery of Denmark (7) University of Antwerp

"I never understand how the lipstick business goes on because lipstick lasts forever" Andy Warhol told Paloma Picasso in a 1980 conversation published in Interview [1]. After an event for a cosmetics company was held in the galleries at the Andy Warhol Museum in 1997, and a vandal kissed Warhol's *Bathtub* (1961) with red lipstick, the prospects of the damage "lasting forever" seemed fateful, as the red smudge could not be removed using the available means. Conservators at the museum turned to NASA, where B. Banks and S. Miller pioneered an atomic oxygen (AO) method to remove the lipstick without physically touching the surface [2] but the AO effects were not investigated. AO is an emerging green non-contact mean and has unique potential for otherwise problematic porous and fragile surfaces that cannot tolerate mechanical "wet" or "dry" cleaning. In the context of Horizon Europe MOXY (2022-

Samples exposed to AO at LEOX

A. Warhol "Bathtub" treatment

2026) and FWO PLASMART (2022-2026) projects and in collaboration with the European Space Agency ESA, the researchers experimented with AO on typical cultural heritage materials and contaminants, using the low Earth orbit oxygen environment simulator LEOX. The samples also included a lipstick, which in the past has been time and again used for art vandalism [3]. The poster focuses on the interim results, characterization and reconstruction of NASA's lipstick treatment. In

this study AO was produced using laser detonation method and the fluence was calculated using the mass loss calculation of the Kapton HN witnesses. Surface morphology was investigated using high-

definition 3D microscopy (HIROX) and SEM, chemical surface changes were investigated using FTIR-ATR and XPS. The lipstick composition contained red iron oxides, which are not affected by AO. However, the AO role was essential, as it converted organic compounds in the lipstick into harmless volatile byproducts (CO, CO₂, H₂O), which enabled minimally invasive dry-removal of the powdery residuum in a second step, repeating NASA's methodology in their treatment of Warhol's *Bathtub*. The findings indicate that AO reacts incrementally with diverse organic compounds on the surface, but at differing rates, which allows formulation of targeted and innovative non-contact treatments, which do not require organic solvents and liquids. The reconstruction of the two-phase cleaning approach was confirmed by inventor B. Banks and the mechanism behind was explained by the new findings, using imaging and analytical tools were not available back in 1997 when the treatment of *Bathtub* took place.

1997 lipstick cleaning (left), 2022 reconstruction cleaning tests

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[1] <https://www.interviewmagazine.com/culture/paloma-picasso-the-diamond-dove-andy-warhol>

[2] Banks, B., Rutledge, S., Karla, M., Norris, M., Real, W., Haytas, C. 1999. Use of an Atmospheric Atomic Oxygen Beam for Restoration of Defaced Paintings, in Proceedings of the 12th ICOM-CC Meeting, 1999, NASA/TM-1999-20941

[3] Banks B., Markevicius T., Olsson, N. 2017. Monoatomic oxygen system for non-contact nanoscale cleaning of vandalized 20th c. modern and contemporary artworks, CeRoArt pp.1-10.